

D5.1 – Data Exploitation Platform Requirements and Design Considerations

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Abstract

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This deliverable presents the Requirement Consolidation Process for the Data Exploitation Platform (DEP) developed within the RI-SCALE project. In order to guide platform development and ensure alignment between technical implementation and scientific use case expectations, a structured process for collecting, organising, reviewing, and formalising system specifications was established. This consolidation process represents one of the main outcomes of the deliverable, providing a common framework for requirement elicitation across both technical work packages (WP2–WP4) and use case contributors (WP5). In addition to the process definition, the deliverable presents the initial set of requirements elicited through this methodology. A total of 88 functional and non-functional requirements were collected, reviewed, and structured with associated metadata to enable traceability and validation planning. Complementing this effort, a set of preliminary high-level design considerations is also provided, outlining the preliminary architecture, user roles, deployment options, and functional domains of the DEP. The process successfully engaged all relevant contributors, producing a balanced distribution of inputs across platform components and work packages. While further alignment and refinements may occur in subsequent phases, the next iteration will primarily focus on validation planning, including the definition of test cases and acceptance criteria based on the consolidated requirements.

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Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CORDEX	Coordinated Regional Downscaling Experiment
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRC	Colo-Rectal Cancer
DEP	Data Exploitation Platform
ESGF	Earth System Grid Federation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GROQ	Generalized Representation for Object Query
IAM	Identity and Access Management
ISR	Incoherent Scatter Radars
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RCS	Radar Cross Section
TCB	Technical Coordination Board
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WCRP	World Climate Research Programme
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable captures the collective understanding, expectations, and early development priorities for the Data Exploitation Platform (DEP) within the RI-SCALE project. It focuses on mapping the needs of both infrastructure providers and scientific end users into a structured set of platform requirements. This synthesis bridges the gap between high-level project objectives and actionable development work, supporting coordination across technical teams and use case integrators.

The document first introduces the overall vision and key design considerations of the DEP, providing essential context for the requirement consolidation process. These preliminary elements define the general objectives, functional domains, and service areas the platform is expected to address. While they help frame the scope of the platform, the primary goal of this deliverable remains the definition and establishment of a consolidation process and framework of operation, in order to enable the systematic elicitation, organisation, and analysis of the platform's requirements.

Through this structured process, 88 functional and non-functional requirements were collected from both technical teams (WP2, WP3, WP4) and use case partners (WP5), ensuring broad coverage of architectural needs, development priorities, and validation objectives. The collected requirements were analysed in terms of:

- Distribution of functional requirements by WP and contributor type.
- Thematic grouping of non-functional requirements (e.g., security, performance, usability).
- Prioritisation of all accepted requirements using the MoSCoW model (Must, Should, Could, Won't).

These outcomes will directly support the definition of the platform validation planning (D5.2), guide implementation planning (D5.3, D5.5), and shape validation activities (D5.4, D5.6). As the main iteration of the Requirements Consolidation Process, the document provides a comprehensive baseline reflecting the current maturity of the platform and use cases. While the primary collection phase is complete, minor refinements to specific requirements may occur as the platform evolves. Any such updates will be tracked and incorporated during the validation planning phase.

1. Introduction

This section outlines the scope and purpose of the deliverable, detailing its role within the overall project structure. It also highlights key dependencies and relationships with other work packages and deliverables.

1.1. Scope and Purpose of the Deliverable

This deliverable presents the RI-SCALE Requirements Consolidation Process, along with the result of this process, which is the initial set of requirements collected, filtered, and reviewed, and presented in [Annex I: Full List of Requirements](#). It also includes the early-stage design considerations for the DEP, developed in the context of WP5 of the RI-SCALE project. The document consolidates technical and use case inputs collected up to M4 and lays the foundation for the architecture, component design, and implementation efforts that will follow.

It captures both functional and non-functional requirements, drawing from internal stakeholders (technical WPs) and domain-specific partners (use case WPs). The document presents an analysis of the current development priorities, maturity levels, and quality expectations of the DEP and its supporting infrastructure. It enables alignment across the development work packages (WP2, WP3, WP4) and helps ensure that the platform's features meet cross-disciplinary and cross-infrastructure needs.

The main limitation of this deliverable reflects the current stage of the project (M4), where both the DEP vision and high-level design considerations remain at an early maturity level. While the requirement elicitation and consolidation process has been successfully completed, and the full set of requirements is presented in Annex I, some limited refinements may still occur as the platform progresses towards implementation. The next steps will primarily focus on validation planning, including the definition of test cases and acceptance criteria. Additional input may also be provided through the activities of the Compliance and Ethics team (WP1) and upcoming use case workshops within WP6.

1.2. Relationship to other WPs and Deliverables

The purpose of this section is to position Deliverable D5.1 within the broader context of the RI-SCALE project. As the first output of WP5, this document consolidates inputs from both technical and use case stakeholders, setting the foundation for the development and validation activities that follow. [Table 1](#) outlines the key WP and deliverables that either contribute to, are supported by, or build upon the content and outcomes of D5.1.

Table 1: D5.1 Relationship to other WPs and Deliverables

D5.1 Relationship to Other WPs and Deliverables		
WP / Deliverable	Focus	Relationship to D5.1
WP2, WP3, WP4	Technical Development Work Packages	These WPs provide the functional and non-functional requirements that D5.1 consolidates and structures. The outcome of D5.1 directly informs the design and development priorities of the platform’s core components, ensuring that technical outputs align with user and system-level needs.
D5.2 – Validation Plan for Use Case Scenarios (M8)	Planning of validation criteria and test scenarios	Builds on D5.1 by translating consolidated requirements into concrete validation plans and KPI definitions.
D5.3 – First DEP Release (M12) & D5.5 – Second DEP Release (M24)	First and second platform implementation cycles	Platform releases are guided by the requirements and design considerations documented in D5.1, establishing the feature set and development focus for each iteration and, more importantly, solidifying the design of the platform.
D5.4 – First Validation Report (M18) & D5.6 – Second Validation Report (M35)	Assessment of platform performance against requirements	These deliverables are informed by the requirement structure established in D5.1, which serves as the baseline for defining testable conditions. The requirements and priorities consolidated here guide the design of validation procedures and scenarios used to assess whether the platform meets its intended functionality and quality attributes.

1.3. Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable is structured into the following sections:

- Section 2 – DEP Vision and High-Level Design Considerations:** This section presents the overarching objectives and guiding principles behind the development of the DEP, outlining the main challenges it addresses and its expected added value for research infrastructures and scientific users. It also introduces the initial design approach and functional domains of the platform, including user roles, deployment models, service responsibilities, and key architectural considerations that set the foundation for the subsequent requirement consolidation;
- Section 3 – Requirement Consolidation Process:** Details the methodology used for collecting, structuring, and reviewing both functional and non-functional requirements. It explains the data model, metadata fields, input sources, and the lifecycle followed during the first iteration of requirement consolidation;

- **Section 4 – Requirements Analysis**: Provides a detailed analysis of the accepted requirements. It includes their classification by type, source, and priority, thematic grouping of non-functional requirements, and discussion of their alignment with platform responsibilities and use case expectations;
- **Section 5 – Conclusion and Next Steps**: Summarise the main outcomes of the deliverable, revisits the platform vision and design implications, and outlines the next steps for validation planning and future refinement of the requirements in upcoming deliverables;
- **Annex I: Full List of Requirements**: Contains the complete tables of accepted functional and non-functional requirements, including all associated metadata. This annex ensures transparency and traceability for technical partners and supports the planning of implementation and validation activities.

2. DEP Vision and High-Level Design Considerations

This section outlines the overarching vision and guiding design principles of the DEP. It introduces the platform's intended role within RI-SCALE, its expected capabilities, and the high-level architectural considerations that influence its development.

2.1. Need for a New RI Service

Advancements in sensors and other digital technologies have turned Research Infrastructures (RIs) into big data factories of the scientific world. More and increasingly bigger scientific datasets are generated at RI facilities and made available in 'data holdings' or 'FAIR data repositories'.

Datasets are offered as downloadable resources in these holdings for both primary and secondary users¹. However, as the size of data holdings and the size and complexity of datasets grow, the re-use of RI data becomes practically impossible without technical knowledge of compute environments, data staging methods, data analysis and data analysis techniques. While some of the RIs deal with this data deluge by incorporating large compute facilities within their infrastructure and offer data through such integrated environments, there are still many RIs that produce data (enable scientists to produce data) but do not offer computational facilities for data analysis and visualisation.

These RIs are the primary beneficiaries of the envisaged DEP, and they face the following common limitations:

1. **Lack of on-site compute:** Limited compute and storage provisioning at RI data holding sites hinders data quality control, data product improvement (incl. FAIR-ification) and the widespread uptake of data by the broader user community for analysis.
2. **Large data downloads and data management:** Large datasets are cumbersome and time-consuming to download for an individual researcher; moreover, separate storage and compute systems may use different access control mechanisms.
3. **Complex software:** Installing and configuring software stacks for running environments for data science (e.g., with AI, Digital twins, Trusted Research Environments (TREs) or Secure Processing Environments (SPEs)) presents a major barrier to users.

¹ The primary user of a dataset is the person who generated the data on the RI facility (e.g. on a microscope, telescope, synchrotron). Secondary users are those who access scientific data that was generated, then shared by primary users. In some cases, secondary users can access data only after a certain 'embargo period' during which only the primary user can use the data and publish papers from it.

These challenges are most pressing for users of distributed RIs, where data is generated and stored in multiple facilities (e.g., BBMRI), and/or RIs with data generation and processing activities that are done by individual users and therefore are unpredictable in scale and time (e.g., Euro-Biolmaging). The acquisition and the analysis might not happen in the same place, which causes inefficiency in the working process. As a result, the reuse and valorisation of the scientific data produced at these facilities often remain under-exploited.

DEPs enable RI data holdings to expand their services with 'online data analysis', by partnering with external compute facilities where data is replicated and served for user analysis.

The next subsections present 4 case studies from the RIs that are in RI-SCALE, highlighting specific challenges that can be tackled with DEPs.

2.2. Case Study: Climate Modelling - ENES

RI overview: IS-ENES serves large community experiments, such as the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), providing climate projections that support the essential World Climate Research Program (WCRP). CMIP has led to the development of the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF), a network of internationally distributed sites that work together as a federated data archive. In this context, ENES acts as the European hub for discovering, accessing and analysing observational data products and climate simulation data, empowering research and supporting policy-making.

Compute-data challenge: The agricultural and insurance sectors can benefit heavily from high-resolution map data (a few hundred metres). However, the current CMIP6/EURO-CORDEX simulations or climate datasets provided by ENES and DestinE are at a much lower resolution. The users would need an infrastructure for downscaling these datasets to a higher resolution. The downscaling could be performed by exploiting AI and statistical models with particular reference to systems based on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). These algorithms process two-dimensional inputs to return high-resolution maps and identify which system returns more reliable maps. Validation will happen in the agriculture and insurance sectors, where future business models can be explored.

2.3. Case Study: Incoherent Radars - EISCAT

RI overview: EISCAT AB operates: (1) EISCAT radars, high-power incoherent scatter radars (ISR), which have been in operation since 1981. EISCAT is the only ISR facility operating a co-located heating facility for active ionospheric modification experiments. Also, a vertical ionospheric sounder (Dynasonde) continuously provides a basic real-time view of the ionospheric structure and is also used to calibrate ISR measurements. (2) EISCAT_3D is the next-generation ISR for investigations of

the near-Earth Geospace environment. Its deployment is currently underway (summer 2025). It will provide volumetric measurements of a large part of the upper atmosphere above Northern Fenno-Scandinavia, including three-dimensional vector measurements of atmospheric dynamics (winds).

Compute-data challenge: Finding anomalies (e.g., rare events or disturbances) in the EISCAT data can be the basis for various data valorisation pathways. One example can be the concept to advance ‘sustainable space use’. With the advent of ‘New Space’ (i.e., miniaturisation leading to ever smaller satellites, as well as rapidly increasing numbers of satellites), overcrowding of orbits increases the risk of collisions, thereby creating more space debris, which eventually can lead to cascading, i.e., causing a chain reaction (Kessler Syndrome). The existing and future EISCAT data could be used to identify events relating to the presence of space objects, establish occurrence statistics and find connections between these events, then identify anthropogenic objects that can threaten sustainable space use, while producing sets of tracks (range, range rate and radar cross section (RCS) measurements) to be used for orbital determination. The challenge requires the integration of massive datasets, machine learning algorithms and a mixed, interdisciplinary team. Other task is intelligent scheduling of radar experiments depending on conditions, based, e.g., on data from complementary instruments.

2.4. Case Study: Biobanking Data - BBMRI

RI overview: BBMRI-ERIC is the European research infrastructure for biobanking bringing together all the main players to boost biomedical research. BBMRI-ERIC currently includes 23 countries and one international organisation, making it one of the largest European research infrastructures. The BBMRI nodes provide various cohorts of data, physically stored within national biobanks. Data discovery is facilitated by the BBMRI Data Portal (<https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/bbmri-sample-and-data-portal/>).

Compute-data challenge: Identifying biomarkers for stratifying colorectal cancer (CRC) risk could facilitate the early detection and treatment of colorectal cancer, offering a more personalised approach to cancer care. Such a histological marker is not known by pathologists today and may only be identified with computational technologies working on very large data sets. Medical experts must be able to tap into external compute and storage resources to develop and validate algorithms, using BBMRI data. Whole slide images from BBMRI Nodes and images from the EUCAIM cancer image infrastructure would be in scope of the work.

2.5. Case Study: Biomedical Image Analysis - Euro-Biolmaging

RI overview: Euro-Biolmaging ERIC is a distributed research infrastructure that offers open access to cutting-edge biological and biomedical imaging technologies, training and data services. Euro-Biolmaging services are provided by 41 Nodes comprising 237 renowned, quality-controlled

imaging facilities. The RI recommends that its user scientists use national or thematic repositories for long-term storage and sharing of their data, such as the BioImage Archive (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/>) or EMPIAR (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar>).

Compute-data challenge: Understanding, categorising and providing access to large cohorts of mixed life sciences imaging data requires computational understanding of those images. The most promising route towards this is through foundation models that capture domain understanding of heterogeneous image data and produce embeddings which support multiple downstream use cases, such as categorisation, similarity search and derived measurements. The challenge is to have high-quality AI models that can extract knowledge from the images and make them richer and better described.

2.6. High-Level Design Considerations

2.6.1. User Roles

A DEP fundamentally acts as an extension of an RI, a new service that is connected to the RI data holding and offers online data analytical services for data processing. In the RI-SCALE project DEPs are specialised for the support of AI-based analysis. [Figure 1](#) presents the main connections and main users of a DEP:

1. **End user** of a DEP is the main beneficiary. They want to discover relevant datasets from an RI to perform data analysis, replicate this data from the holding to the compute facility that operates the DEP environment, and choose a pre-configured, pre-trained AI model to analyse the data with inference runs. Typically, end users have direct access to the DEP and they are authorised RI users who run the models on data and share the outputs with other authorised users.
2. **Model developers** create and deploy new AI models within the DEP. They either use off-the-shelf 3rd party models, or develop their own models, then train the models with RI data, and share the validated models via the DEP with the end users.
3. **DEP operator** deploys, configures and operates the DEP environment within a compute centre, and ensures its proper connections to external systems. These connections include links to the data holding(s), to AI-model stores and to identity management systems that are supported by the specific DEP installation.

Figure 1: Main Connections and User Scenarios of a DEP

2.6.2. Deployment Options

DEPs are jointly provisioned by e-infrastructure and RI institutions, with long term operational models that will be developed in the last year of the project (in 2027). We envisage a DEP installation to be customised for a certain community, where its capabilities are defined by the datasets and AI models that are offered for data analysis:

- The datasets required by a community dictate to the DEP operator which data holding(s) to connect/configure for the DEP.
- The AI models required by a community dictate to the DEP operator which model repository (or models) to make accessible in the DEP.

The data holding - DEP connection is an important consideration in the overall design. We can envisage four configuration options depending on the type of RI, and depending on the capacity allocation policy the DEP needs to work with. The four DEP configuration options are summarised in [Table 2](#) below with their pros and cons.

Table 2: The Four Possible DEP Configuration Options

DEP Configurations			
Graphical representation	Description	Pros.	Cons.
	1 DEP is connected to 1 data holding. E.g. ENES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplest configuration. • Supports any end user from any location. 	Requires extra efforts with 3rd party interoperability, i.e., avoiding siloing and having to take into account the design phase.
	1 DEP is connected to multiple data holdings. E.g. EISCAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Works for RIs that have/need multiple data holdings. • Supports any end user from any location. • Removes data silos within/across RIs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires complex data staging and integration support. • Requires bigger storage and compute capacity in a single site. • Requires more complex IT security and privacy configuration.
	Multiple DEPs are connected to the same data holding. E.g. Euro-Biolmaging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can segment the users into multiple DEPs (e.g. one per country). • Requires smaller compute capacity . 	Requires more operational effort
	Multiple DEPs are connected to multiple data holdings. E.g. BBMRI	Works even when the RI has multiple repositories, and is supported by multiple compute centres	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most complex setup with most effort intensive operation. • Requires more complex IT security and privacy configuration.

2.6.3. Main Functional Pillars

DEPs require the integration of four main functional areas, and these are summarised in [Table 3](#). The RI-SCALE consortium includes technology providers for each of the areas, and their software will need to be integrated and extended within each area to tackle the respective requirements.

Table 3: Main Functional Pillars and Implementation Technologies for the DEP

Main Functional Pillars and Implementation Technologies for the DEP		
Functional area	Main requirement	Implementation technologies
Data lifecycle management	Ability to replicate datasets from the data holdings to the DEP environment (making data accessible to AI applications), AND	RUCIO, FTS, ESGF Data Statistics service, ESGF Search

	ability to delete dataset replicas from the DEP after those are not used/needed any longer (to preserve storage space on the compute resources).	
Artificial Intelligence	Environments that support the importing of externally developed and validated AI models (so they become executable for inference within the DEP), AND/OR also the development, training and validation of AI models within the DEP (so they can be trained on data coming from the connected data holdings).	itwinai, AI4HPC, BioEngine, Biolmage Model Zoo, Hypha
Access control (Trust and identity management)	Management systems that enable the separation of user sessions from each other enable access to the different components of the system in a coherent and user-friendly manner.	Check-in, Keycloak, Federation Registry, INDIGO-IAM, Life Science AAI
Credit management	Components that enable DEP operators and end users to measure and track resource consumption over time, to translate usage into 'credits', and to enable/suspend user access according to pre-defined credit policies.	ARGO Accounting

The baseline functions must be complemented with additional capabilities that cut across the whole DEP, most importantly:

- **Resource discovery:** enabling end users and model developers to browse datasets and AI models within a DEP;
- **Operation monitoring and optimisation:** empowering DEP operators to see 'what is happening' within the system, and to enable operational optimisation, such as setting shorter lifetime to replicate data (to lower storage consumption), optimise 'DEP greenness' by installing/configuring different HW and different allocation policies for CPU/GPU/storage, accelerators, etc;
- **User interfaces:** The various technologies that are listed in [Table 3](#) already come with their own interfaces; these need to be assessed and aligned/integrated in a coherent manner to select those that will be exposed from the DEP towards its users. We envisage a gradual improvement in the DEP in this respect, with less integration of elements in the first version, and gradual strengthening of the components afterwards.

2.6.4. Non-functional Considerations

Besides the functional capabilities, DEPs need to be designed with the following non-functional considerations in mind:

- The overall development requires a gradual approach with a continuous feedback loop between the DEP developers and the RI communities to achieve a flexible and suitable service candidate for RIs.
- The end user experience must be based on the needs of scientific end users and research infrastructure (RI) users. DEPs will include several existing applications with their respective user interfaces. Users of DEPs have their own applications, standards, and working methods, which may differ significantly from those of other communities. Therefore, the system design must clearly consider the scientific user's interaction flow. This should be documented using user journey diagrams or walkthroughs to support platform usability design in future iterations.
- The different building blocks should use industry protocols and frameworks that can suit multiple communities. Avoid home-grown, workforce-intensive solutions that will be hard to sustain in the long term.
- User support will be critical in the early uptake and validation period and needs to be organised as a joint effort between RIs and e-infrastructures, with clear interfaces and areas of responsibility among the teams.
- Performance, reliability, and availability of the DEP depend both on the platform itself and on the systems and applications integrated with it. Therefore, it is essential to keep these factors prioritized across all technical WPs and use cases. The upcoming deliverables, D2.1, D3.1, D4.1, and D5.2, should explicitly address these critical system design elements.
- The DEP's architecture is distributed and federated, providing a foundation for modularity, scalability, and adaptability to change. When developing and building the DEP, it is also important to consider sustainability aspects, particularly in terms of usability and long-term maintainability.
- The DEP will be designed to handle both sensitive data (such as personal or health-related information) and non-sensitive data. Given the strict regulations surrounding sensitive data security and privacy, these considerations must be integral to the system design. Adopting established security standards (such as ISO/IEC 27001) is recommended as a starting point for the DEP's security and privacy framework across all data types. Furthermore, the design must incorporate testability, observability, and logging capabilities to ensure effective monitoring, auditing, and validation of the platform.

3. Requirements Overview and Consolidation Process

The requirement consolidation process was defined to ensure traceability between the high-level vision of the DEP (as described in [Section 2](#)), its architectural design and functional domains (outlined in Section 3), and the actual development and validation efforts carried out by the consortium. To achieve this, the process incorporated inputs from both technical and use case contributors and was structured around key metadata fields and requirement attributes that reflect the platform's modular architecture and service responsibilities. Specific attention was given to defining appropriate sources, classifications, and component mappings to maintain alignment between envisioned functionalities, cross-WP developments, and scientific needs. This section details how these considerations shaped the overall requirement lifecycle (from collection to review) and provided a structured framework for tracking the evolution of requirements throughout the project.

3.1. Objectives of the Requirement Consolidation Activity

The requirement consolidation activity in RI-SCALE serves as the foundational mechanism for aligning platform development with both the high-level goals of the project and the operational needs of its stakeholders (use-cases). The core objectives of this activity are as follows:

- **Translate strategic goals into actionable specifications:** The requirement engineering process ensures that project KPIs and strategic targets are systematically translated into functional and non-functional platform specifications. This includes aspects such as data processing, AI model execution, access control, and platform interoperability.
- **Enable structured and traceable platform development:** By systematically collecting, structuring, and tagging requirements with standardized metadata, the project ensures that all developments are traceable back to their origin (e.g., use cases, WP contributions, stakeholder needs). This also supports validation planning and release alignment.
- **Facilitate cross-WP technical integration:** The process creates a shared framework for WP2 (Data Lifecycle Management), WP3 (Scalable AI), and WP4 (Access Management) to define their own components in relation to shared objectives. It ensures that the individual developments form a coherent and interoperable DEP architecture, and, most importantly, that these technical developments are aligned with the scientific and technical use case requirements that drive the project.
- **Capture needs from both internal and external stakeholders:** The process is designed to include technical insights from project partners (internal WPs and use cases) as well as input

from external RIs, data spaces, and domain-specific communities through co-design workshops.

- **Support validation and prioritization:** Requirement engineering underpins the planning of scientific and technical validations (T5.2 and T5.3) and provides the baseline for requirement prioritization strategies, such as MoSCoW classification.
- **Establish change control and adaptability:** By linking requirements to time frames, dependencies, and validation criteria, the process supports controlled updates and adaptation to evolving technical and stakeholder feedback during the project lifecycle.

Overall, this activity ensures that the development of the DEP remains user-driven, technically feasible, and aligned with the impact expectations of the RI-SCALE project.

3.2. Requirement Consolidation Process

The requirement consolidation process will take place in two main phases within the context of WP5 deliverables:

- In D5.1, the focus is on capturing the initial set of requirements and technical specifications. This early-stage consolidation draws on inputs from internal stakeholders, including technical work packages (WP2–WP4), scientific and technical use case leaders, and project KPIs. The goal is to establish a coherent baseline for the architecture and functionality of the DEP, enabling traceable and feasible development from the outset.
- In D5.2, the process is extended to incorporate external contributors (e.g., stakeholders engaged through WP6), as well as ethics and compliance requirements from WP1. Furthermore, as the technical work progresses and the use cases mature, the requirement set will be refined and expanded where needed. Crucially, this phase will introduce test cases and acceptance criteria for each validated requirement, forming the foundation of the RI-SCALE Validation Plan. This will ensure that all developments are verifiable, measurable, and directly linked to the expected outcomes defined in the project KPIs.

Throughout both phases, requirements are contextualized within the RI-SCALE technical ecosystem. Leveraging Confluence and Jira, the project enforces a transparent, iterative process for requirement tracking, validation, and change management, ensuring that each specification is actionable, validated, and aligned with the broader objectives of the project.

3.2.1. Requirement Lifecycle

The lifecycle of a requirement in RI-SCALE follows a structured, multi-stage process designed to ensure traceability, quality control, and alignment with both technical feasibility and project-level objectives. This process is executed and monitored via the Confluence and Jira platforms, which serve as the central tools for requirement management.

Collection

New requirements are formally collected through a combination of stakeholder engagement activities, including structured focus groups and co-design workshops. Inputs originate from internal technical discussions, project KPIs, use cases, development and management teams, as well as technical specifications. All requirements are submitted manually into the Jira page as issues by designated Collectors or authorized partners. At this stage, the requirements are not yet filtered or validated.

Filtering

Submitted requirements undergo an initial filtering step performed by the Collectors. This includes:

- Removal of duplicates.
- Merging or splitting of requirements when necessary.
- Elimination of entries that do not constitute actionable system features or enhancements.

Requirements that pass the filtering step are categorized and moved to dedicated Confluence pages corresponding to specific components (e.g., DEP platform, AI solutions).

Review

Requirements that pass the filtering stage are then reviewed in detail. This review is carried out by relevant WP experts and involves:

- Evaluation of completeness, feasibility, and technical alignment.
- Classification as functional or non-functional.
- Prioritization based on the MoSCoW method.

Any further approval or rejection may occur at this stage as needed.

Rejection or Approval

During both the filtering and review phases, requirements are either:

- **Approved:** if they are complete, feasible, and aligned with the project objectives. Approved requirements are moved forward for technical planning.
- **Rejected:** if they are incomplete, infeasible, or out of scope. Rejected items are clearly marked in Confluence, and Reviewers must provide a justification for rejection.

Validation and Implementation

Requirements that progress to implementation are transitioned into the **validation phase**, where:

- The requirements of Jira issues are expanded to contain:
 - Acceptance criteria and
 - Validation test cases are defined.
- Development teams review the validation test cases as well as the acceptance criteria and move the requirements

Once a requirement is implemented and passes validation checks, it is marked as **DONE** in Jira, completing its lifecycle. [Figure 2](#) below presents the graphical representation of this lifecycle, illustrating the flow from collection to final validation. It is important to state again that the definition of the validation plan and test cases, as well as the acceptance criteria, will be defined in the context of the validation planning of D5.2.

Figure 2: RI-SCALE Requirement Consolidation and Validation Planning Process

3.2.2. Roles and Responsibilities

The definition of roles and responsibilities within the RI-SCALE requirement consolidation process follows a structured, traceable model designed to support operational clarity and foster alignment across the project's technical and validation activities. This approach is grounded in the Description of Action (DoA), which highlights the need for coordinated development across technical work packages (WP2–WP4) and continuous feedback from scientific and stakeholder communities (WP5–WP6). Given the scope and complexity of the DEP, responsibilities have been assigned to ensure that requirements are collected, reviewed, implemented, and validated by the appropriate actors at each stage. The process emphasizes alignment between the evolving technical components and the needs of the use cases, as well as consistency with project-level objectives and KPIs.

Key roles (**Collectors, Reviewers, Validators/Integrators, and Developers**) have been defined to cover the full lifecycle of requirements. These roles are fulfilled by WP leaders, task leads, use case providers, and development teams, each contributing domain-specific expertise. Oversight is

provided by the **Task 5.1 leader** and the **Technical Coordination Board (TCB)** to ensure coherence across WPs and integration into the project's broader strategy.

This structure was created considering the needs of both internal and external stakeholders, aiming to support a robust and transparent workflow that links use case requirements with technical implementation and measurable validation outcomes. [Table 4](#) summarises the core roles, their responsibilities, and the corresponding actors in the RI-SCALE requirement lifecycle.

Table 4: Roles and Responsibilities in the Requirements Elicitation and Validation Lifecycle

Roles and Responsibilities		
Roles	Responsibilities	RI-SCALE Representatives
Collectors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for gathering requirements from various sources, including internal and external stakeholders, technical teams, and project Use cases and KPI's. Insert all collected requirements into the Confluence/Jira New Requirement page/Issues for initial tracking. Ensure requirements are clearly described and categorized before passing them to the Reviewers. 	<p>Use Case Leaders: Collect use case-specific requirements</p> <p>Task 5.1 Leader: Overview and management of the process</p> <p>WP5 Leader: Oversees the use-case requirements elicitation</p> <p>Technical & Development Teams (WP2, WP3, WP4): collects development specific functional and non-functional requirements</p>
Reviewers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for filtering requirements. Remove duplicate, redundant, or unclear requirements and refine them before review. Assess each requirement's completeness, feasibility, and priority based on project KPIs. Categorize requirements as functional or non-functional and determine prioritization using the MoSCoW method. Assign approved requirements to relevant sections in Confluence and document justifications for rejected requirements. 	<p>Task 5.1 Leader: Oversees the process.</p> <p>Use Case Leaders: Sanitize and remove duplicates for Use Case requirements.</p> <p>Technical & Development Teams (WP2, WP3, WP4): Reviews the technical feasibility, priority and timing</p> <p>Technical Coordination Board (TCB): Ensures alignment with KPIs and project goals.</p>
Validator/Integrator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Responsible for defining and tracking test cases and acceptance criteria for each approved requirement. Ensure that each requirement is transitioned into Jira with clear validation parameters. 	<p>Task 5.1 Leader: Oversees validation planning.</p> <p>Technical Coordination Board (TCB): Ensures system integration alignment with the KPIs.</p> <p>Technical & Development Teams (WP2, WP3, WP4): Provide</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitor testing progress and ensure all validation processes align with project KPIs. 	platform-specific validation plan and test cases.
Developer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement and test approved requirements according to defined specifications. Ensure each requirement meets the acceptance criteria before transitioning it to completion. Update Jira issue statuses accordingly throughout the development and testing phases. Report results and ensure that validated requirements are properly documented before changing status to "DONE". 	<p>Technical & Development Teams (WP2, WP3, WP4): Actuate the validation process and report results.</p> <p>Technical Coordination Board (TCB): Oversee the validation process.</p>

3.2.3. Requirement Sources

Requirements in RI-SCALE are collected from a broad range of sources to ensure coverage of all project dimensions, from technical implementation and scientific use cases to legal compliance and external validation. Inputs originate from internal technical teams and use case leaders to align development activities with concrete operational needs. Risk & Compliance (WP1) contributes data protection and ethics-related requirements to ensure legal and regulatory alignment. External stakeholders provide feedback through co-design activities and broader consultations to maintain relevance and interoperability.

In the initial phase of the requirement engineering process, all primary sources contributed except for Risk & Compliance (WP1-T1.3) and the co-design workshops led under WP6. These will be formally integrated in the second phase (D5.2), once technical components and use case implementations have reached greater maturity. [Table 5](#) summarises the main requirement sources, their purpose, and the associated collection methods.

Table 5: Requirement Sources

Requirement Sources		
Requirement Source	Why is It Important?	How to Collect?
Project KPIs	Ensure alignment with measurable objectives.	Map KPIs to system requirements.
Internal Stakeholders (WP2-5)	Ensure DEP technical feasibility and use case adaptation	Partner meetings (focus groups)

External Stakeholders (WP6)	Ensure user adoption & interoperability.	Workshops, industry consultations, surveys.
Technical Specifications (WP2-4)	Leverage existing AI & DEP models.	Review state-of-the-art systems.
Risk & Compliance(WP1)	Ensure security & legal alignment.	Data compliance and ethics-related requirements from WP1 (T1.3)

3.2.4. Requirement Fields and Metadata

To ensure transparency, traceability, and consistency throughout the requirement lifecycle, each requirement in RI-SCALE is captured and managed using a set of structured fields. These fields are implemented in Jira and Confluence, forming the metadata backbone that enables systematic collection, review, prioritization, and validation. The fields are grouped into three main categories, each serving a distinct purpose in the overall process:

- **Operational fields**, which enable tracking of responsibility and progress,
- **Categorization and description fields**, which define the nature and context of each requirement, and
- **Tracking and validation fields**, which support quality control, implementation planning, and verification.

The following subsections describe the rationale and function of each field group.

3.2.4.1 Operational Fields

Operational fields provide the foundational metadata needed to manage each requirement throughout its lifecycle. These fields track the origin, responsible partners, and current status of a requirement, allowing for accountability, lifecycle visibility, and communication across WPs. They are essential for coordinating activities across distributed teams and for enabling filtering and reporting functionalities.

Table 6: RI-SCALE Requirement Operational Fields

Operational Fields	
Field Name	Definition
ID/KEY	Each requirement will be stored as a Jira issue with an auto-generated issue key (e.g., REQ-001, REQ-002, etc.).
Partner Introducing Requirement	This field identifies the organization that submitted the requirement in Jira. It is used for operational tracking, ensuring that the correct partner can be contacted if clarification or modifications are needed (e.g., EGI, CERN, JNP, etc).

<p>Status</p>	<p>The Status field is an operational tracking field used to monitor the progress of each requirement throughout the review and validation process. It ensures clear visibility into the requirements lifecycle and helps stakeholders understand its current state.</p> <p>Filtering – The requirement is being initially assessed for relevance, duplicates, or potential merging.</p> <p>Reviewing – The requirement has passed the initial filtering and is under evaluation by technical teams for feasibility, completeness, and alignment with project objectives.</p> <p>Accepted – The requirement has been reviewed and approved for implementation. It will be included in the project scope and development planning.</p> <p>Rejected – The requirement does not meet project criteria, is technically infeasible, or is out of scope. Justification for rejection must be documented.</p> <p>Under Development – Active work is being done to implement the requirement within the DEP system.</p> <p>Completed (Ready for validation) – The development work has finished, and the requirement is ready for validation.</p> <p>Under Validation - the development has finished and the validation according to the test cases performed.</p> <p>Validated – The requirement has successfully passed validation, ensuring that it meets all expected criteria and is fully functional.</p>
<p>Rejection Rational</p>	<p>This field is mandatory whenever a requirement’s Status is set to "Rejected". It ensures transparency by documenting the reason a requirement was not accepted, helping avoid misunderstandings and tracking decisions for future reference.</p>

3.2.4.2 Categorization/Description Fields

Categorization and description fields define what a requirement is about and how it fits into the overall system. These include the requirement type, associated component, and a clear textual description. This grouping ensures each requirement is understandable, appropriately classified, and placed in the right technical context, which is critical for effective review and prioritization.

Table 7: RI-SCALE Requirement Categorisation/Description Fields

Categorization/Description Fields	
Field Name	Definition
<p>Type</p>	<p>Specifies whether the requirement is Functional (describes what the system should do) or Non-functional (describes performance, security, interoperability, etc.).</p>
<p>Source</p>	<p>The sources of requirements can be internal (originating within the RI-SCALE project) or external (coming from stakeholders outside the consortium). Internal Sources (Project Partners)</p>

	<p>These originate from RI-SCALE partners and internal technical teams:</p> <p>[ITT] Internal – Technical Team (Requirements proposed by WP2, WP3, or WP4 teams regarding platform architecture, AI models, and security mechanisms).</p> <p>[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC) (Requirements derived from the eight scientific use cases, related to climate, health, space science, and other domain applications).</p> <p>[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC) (Requirements originating from the four technical use cases, focusing on AI scalability, AI model optimization, hardware benchmarking, etc.).</p> <p>[IRC] Internal – Risk & Compliance (WP1) Data compliance and ethics-related requirements from WP1(T1.3)</p> <p>External Sources (Stakeholder Input). These come from consultations, workshops, or external partners providing feedback on DEP development:</p> <p>[EW] External – Stakeholder Workshops (Requirements gathered from co-design workshops and external discussions with RI operators, AI research networks, industry, and EOSC/Gaia-X representatives).</p>
Component That Fulfils It	<p>The system, module, or framework responsible for satisfying the requirement (e.g., AI model hub, data orchestration services, etc).</p> <p>Data Orchestration Service (WP2-T2.1). Data Preparation Module (WP2-T2.2). Data Discovery & Popularity Service (WP2-T2.3). Data Holdings Integration Framework (WP2-T2.4). Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5). AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1). AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2). AI for Environmental Science (WP3-T3.3). AI for Health and Life Sciences (WP3-T3.4). Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1). Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2). Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3). Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4).</p>
Description	A clear and concise explanation of what the requirement entails.
Rationale	Justification for why the requirement is needed (e.g., compliance with GDPR, addressing a specific technical challenge, improving user experience).
Priority	Importance level of the requirement, typically categorized as Must, Should, Could, or Will not (aligned with MoSCoW prioritization).
Additional Comments	Any extra details, clarifications, or discussions related to the requirement.

3.2.4.3 Tracking & Validation Fields

Tracking and validation fields support downstream planning and quality assurance. They allow the project team to define dependencies, expected timelines, acceptance criteria, and validation outcomes. These fields are key to ensuring that approved requirements are not only implemented but also verifiably meet project expectations and compliance standards. As mentioned before in the initial requirement collection, this information will not be included in these fields are provisioned for the validation planning (D5.2) and will be filled when the DEP design is more mature.

Table 8: RI-SCALE Requirement Tracking and Validation Fields

Tracking and Validation Fields	
Field Name	Definition
Dependencies	Other requirements, components, or external factors that must be in place for this requirement to be fulfilled.
Time Frame	Expected timeline or project milestone when the requirement should be implemented (e.g., RI-SCALE (1 st release - 2 nd release)).
Test Case / Acceptance Criteria	The criteria or steps used to validate that the requirement has been successfully implemented (e.g., specific tests, expected outputs, performance benchmarks).
Validation Results	The outcome of testing or validation (e.g., confirmed success, challenges encountered, alternative approaches taken).

4. Analysis of Collected Requirements

This section presents the consolidated outcome of the requirement gathering process. It includes an overview of the accepted requirements, their classification into functional and non-functional types, their alignment with technical work packages, and their relevance to platform design. The analysis is supported by visual summaries and statistical insights, while the full requirement set is provided in Annex I: Full List of Requirements.

4.1. Requirements Consolidation General Overview

From the structured consolidation process described earlier, a total of 97 requirements were submitted by internal contributors and use case partners. Out of these, 88 were accepted following the filtering and review procedure. The remaining 9 were rejected due to duplication and scope misalignment.

Figure 3: RI-SCALE Overall Requirement Acceptance Status

Out of the 88 accepted requirements, 60 are functional and 28 are non-functional. This distribution reflects the current stage of the project, where emphasis has been placed on defining the core functionalities of the DEP. Nevertheless, the presence of a substantial set of non-functional requirements demonstrates that early attention has also been given to performance, usability, security, and other platform-wide quality considerations. This balance lays a solid foundation for both implementation and validation in the upcoming phases. Detailed insights into both functional and non-functional requirements are provided in the dedicated subsections that follow (4.3 Analysis of Non-Functional Requirements and 4.4 Prioritisation Considerations).

The chart presented in [Figure 4](#) illustrates how requirements are distributed across the three main technical work packages. WP4 shows the highest total volume, with a substantial presence of both functional and non-functional requirements. This indicates a balanced focus on both feature

development and platform-level quality considerations in the area of access and identity management. In contrast, the requirements associated with WP2 and WP3 are almost exclusively functional, reflecting an early emphasis on defining system capabilities for data orchestration and AI-driven processing.

Figure 4: Distribution of Requirements by WP

Figure 5: Distribution of Requirements by Source

The requirement source distribution (Figure 5) reveals a nearly even split between contributions from the Technical Team (45 requirements) and the Use Case partners (43 requirements, both from

scientific and technical Use Cases). While the technical team accounts for a slightly higher number, the difference is marginal, underscoring a collaborative and balanced approach to platform design. This distribution confirms that the internal development is not occurring in isolation, but rather in active coordination with scientific and operational use case input. Such alignment is essential to ensure that the DEP architecture reflects not only technical feasibility but also real-world applicability and user relevance from the outset.

Overall MoSCoW Priority Distribution

Figure 6: Requirement Prioritization Summary

The prioritization breakdown in [Figure 6](#) reveals that a clear majority of the requirements are marked as “Must”, indicating high alignment with critical system needs. This strong emphasis on mandatory features is typical at this stage of platform development, where establishing core functionalities is essential. A smaller but relevant portion of requirements is tagged as “Should” or “Could”, representing desirable or optional features that may be addressed in subsequent iterations or depending on resource availability.

4.2. Analysis of Functional Requirements

Functional requirements describe the specific capabilities, services, or behaviours that the DEP must support. They define what the system should do, such as data ingestion, AI model inference, access management, or orchestration workflows, as perceived by both implementation teams and use case contributors. These requirements are actionable, traceable, and form the foundation for design, development, and validation of the platform. As described in [Section 3.2.3 Requirement Sources](#), inputs were collected from the technical teams of WP2, WP3, and WP4, as well as from both scientific and technical use cases. This diverse set of inputs ensures that the functional expectations for the DEP address both core component development and use case alignment.

To better understand the distribution of functional requirements, the chart depicted in [Figure 7](#) illustrates how these requirements are split across the three main technical WP. Each bar is further broken down by source, distinguishing between internal component development by the technical teams and functional inputs from scientific and technical use cases.

Figure 7: Functional Requirement Distribution

Out of the total 60 accepted functional requirements, WP4 holds the largest share with 24 entries, followed by WP2 and WP3, each with 18. In WP2 and WP3, the majority of functional requirements stem from use case contributors (14 out of 18 in both cases), reflecting the close involvement of domain partners in shaping the AI and data orchestration components. WP4, on the other hand, is more heavily influenced by the internal technical team, which accounts for 17 out of its 24 requirements. This breakdown provides insight into the balance between technical platform-level design and domain-specific needs, helping to structure the detailed analysis that follows. For each WP, we will first examine the functional priorities defined by the internal teams, followed by an overview of what is expected from the use case side.

4.2.1. DEP Data Lifecycle Management Requirement Considerations

The chart depicted in [Figure 8](#) illustrates how WP2 functional requirements are distributed across its constituent tasks, broken down by source (Technical Team vs Use Case). Out of the total 18 functional requirements aligned with WP2, the majority (14) originate from use case contributors, while only 4 are submitted by the technical team. Notably, T2.1 and T2.2 (the full names of the tasks are presented in [Table 7](#)) are covered exclusively by use case input.

Figure 8: WP2 functional requirement distribution

Technical Team Contributions

The technical team contributes functional requirements to T2.3, T2.4, and T2.5 (the full names of the tasks are presented in [Table 7](#)), reflecting targeted efforts to support data querying, access provisioning, and interoperability of services. These priorities indicate a focus on enabling backend capabilities required to expose, federate, and manage structured data access across the platform. Collectively, these technical specifications shape the enabling infrastructure for making curated datasets reliably available across DEP components.

Use Case Contributions

Use case partners provide the majority of WP2 functional requirements, shaping all five tasks, including exclusive input in T2.1 and T2.2. This dominance is not coincidental; the technologies involved in these areas (data ingestion and orchestration) are considered mature, and the main challenge is to adapt them to domain-specific needs. As a result, no new specifications were added by the technical teams in these areas. The use case requirements focus on automated pipelines, metadata control, dataset traceability, and complex ingestion scenarios, ensuring that data lifecycle mechanisms are compatible with real operational workflows in scientific environments.

4.2.2. Scalable AI Solutions Requirement Considerations

The chart presented below showcases the distribution of WP3 functional requirements across its four constituent tasks. A total of 18 functional requirements are aligned with WP3. Of these, 14 requirements originate from Use Case contributors, while the remaining 4 requirements come from the Technical Team. The tasks with the highest functional input are T3.1 (7 total) and T3.4 (5 total), indicating concentrated focus on AI execution and explainability (the full names of the tasks are presented in [Table 7](#)). This reflects a strong alignment of platform development with user needs, while still preserving essential architectural inputs from technical partners.

Figure 9: WP3 Functional Requirement Distribution

Technical Team Contributions

The Technical Team provided 2 requirements each in T3.1 and T3.2, representing a focused effort to ensure AI model integration, registry support, and execution interfaces are architecturally sound and interoperable. These contributions define the scaffolding required to support AI lifecycle management in DEP, covering inference infrastructure, containerization approaches, and system-level integration layers essential for scalable and reproducible workflows.

Use Case Contributions

The Use Case partners contributed the majority of functional inputs to WP3, spanning all four tasks. Specifically, T3.1 received 5, T3.2 received 2, T3.3 received 2, and T3.4 received all 5 of its requirements from use case teams. These requirements express strong needs around domain-specific model training, adaptation workflows, performance benchmarking, explainability, and reusability of AI components. Their diversity illustrates the expected flexibility of the DEP AI layer to serve varied scientific domains, including climate modelling, medical imaging, and space science.

4.2.3. Access Management Technologies requirement considerations

The chart presented below displays the distribution of WP4 functional requirements across its four constituent tasks. A total of 24 functional requirements are assigned to WP4. Of these, 7 requirements are submitted by the Technical Team, while 17 originate from Use Case contributors (including both scientific and technical use cases). WP4-T4.2 receives the largest number of inputs overall (8), followed by T4.1 (7), T4.4 (6), and T4.3 (3). The data shows that while foundational access and compliance layers are predominantly defined by the technical team, the Credit Management

System (T4.4) is driven exclusively by use case demands (the full names of the tasks are presented in [Table 7](#)).

Figure 10: WP4 Functional Requirement Distribution

Technical Team Contributions

The Technical Team contributes 17 functional requirements, primarily targeting T4.1, T4.2, and T4.3. These cover access control enforcement, identity federation, authorization flows, and compliance with European data regulations. In T4.1, technical inputs focus on session isolation and role-based access. In T4.2, they define interfaces for integration with Gaia-X and EOSC authentication policies. T4.3 covers encryption, privacy enforcement, and secure auditing. No technical requirements are associated with T4.4.

Use Case Contributions

Use Case partners provide 7 functional requirements, with a focused cluster of 6 in T4.4, fully defining the Credit Management System. These include:

- Resource usage tracking (CPU/GPU/Storage);
- Environmental impact monitoring;
- Credit conversion models;
- User feedback mechanisms.

An additional requirement is contributed to T4.1, addressing access granularity and provisioning. No use case inputs are recorded for T4.2 or T4.3. This confirms that while the underlying access infrastructure is led by the technical team, use cases play a defining role in shaping user-facing credit enforcement and resource governance mechanisms within DEP.

4.3. Analysis of Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements define the quality attributes and operational constraints of the DEP, such as performance, security, scalability, interoperability, and usability. While functional requirements determine *what* the system should do, non-functional requirements govern *how* it should behave, shaping its architecture, operational stability, and trustworthiness.

In RI-SCALE (as depicted in [Figure 11](#)), a total of 28 non-functional requirements were collected and accepted. The majority of non-functional requirements are aligned with WP4 (21 total), which focuses on access and identity management, a domain where quality attributes like security, policy enforcement, and user control are critical. Of these, 18 were submitted by the technical team, indicating strong internal attention to infrastructure integrity and governance.

Non-Functional Requirement Sources per Work Package

Figure 11: Non-Functional Requirements Distribution

WP3 includes 5 non-functional requirements, primarily contributed by use case partners, highlighting interest in explainability, trust, and compliance within AI processing. WP2 accounts for only 2 non-functional requirements, evenly split between technical and use case inputs, suggesting that most concerns in data lifecycle orchestration have been covered under functional definitions or will be specified later as implementations mature.

In order to meaningfully assess the non-functional requirements, it was necessary to classify them into thematic categories. This classification was derived through a close reading of each requirement’s description and rationale, allowing us to group them according to the underlying quality attribute they address. The resulting thematic distribution provides a clearer picture of system-level concerns and their alignment with architectural responsibilities.

Figure 12: Thematical Distribution of Non-Functional Requirements per WP

The chart in [Figure 12](#) presents the distribution of non-functional requirements (NFRs) across four thematic categories, Performance & Scalability, Security & Compliance, Interoperability & Integration, and Usability & Maintainability, as contributed by the technical WPs (WP2, WP3, WP4).

Performance & Scalability

This category includes a significant number of non-functional requirements, emphasizing the platform’s ability to handle high data volumes, support real-time workflows, and enable efficient use of computational resources. These requirements are mainly contributed by WP3 and WP4. WP3 focuses on ensuring scalable and efficient AI model execution, particularly in resource-aware environments and high-performance computing contexts. WP4 complements this with performance expectations for access and identity management components, such as authorization systems that must remain responsive and reliable under increased user and data load.

Security & Compliance

This is the largest thematic group among the non-functional requirements. It reflects a strong and consistent focus on secure access, policy enforcement, identity federation, and compliance with European data protection frameworks (e.g., GDPR). These requirements are predominantly contributed by WP4 (logical outcome considering the nature and focus of the tasks within this WP), which is responsible for access control infrastructure and policy-driven authorization mechanisms. The concentration of contributions in this theme underscores the platform’s need to operate in sensitive, cross-institutional environments where user identity, data integrity, and legal compliance are essential.

Interoperability & Integration

Although smaller in number, this category captures critical requirements aimed at ensuring platform components can interface effectively with each other and with external systems. These include integration with AAI (Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure) services, adoption of standard protocols, and support for federated access patterns. Most of these requirements are contributed by WP4 and align with the goal of embedding the DEP within a broader ecosystem of research infrastructures.

Usability & Maintainability

This group includes requirements that address user interaction, intuitiveness, clarity, and manageability of the platform. Although limited in volume at this stage, they reflect an important concern: reducing friction for end users (particularly researchers and developers) when interacting with the platform's services. Contributions come from across all WPs, with emphasis on the need for transparent interfaces, simplified workflows, and automation to reduce manual overhead in recurring tasks.

Taken together, the thematic distribution confirms a balance across both operational and user-centric qualities of the system. While Performance & Scalability and Security & Compliance dominate in quantity, the presence of targeted Interoperability and Usability requirements demonstrates that contributors are also attentive to cross-platform integration and end-user experience. It is important to note that this analysis reflects the current stage of the project; in the next iteration of the deliverables, both the platform and the use cases are expected to be more mature. This will support the elicitation of more specific and actionable requirements in the areas of interoperability and usability.

4.4. Prioritisation Considerations

Requirement prioritization, based on the MoSCoW method (Must, Should, Could, Won't), offers a structured way to assess the urgency and criticality of both functional and non-functional requirements. This classification helps informing the planning of implementation phases, clarifying trade-offs, and aligning stakeholder expectations around what is essential versus what is optional. [Figure 13](#) below presents the distribution of requirement priorities across the contributing WPs (WP2, WP3, WP4). Each bar is segmented by priority level, showing how each WP balances critical developments against more flexible or desirable features. Specifically:

- **WP4** has the highest number of "Must" requirements, which aligns with its responsibility for access control, identity management, and security domains that demand strict guarantees and regulatory compliance.
- **WP3** displays a mix of "Must" and "Should" priorities, reflecting the performance and explainability expectations tied to AI models and resource-aware execution.

- **WP2** has the fewest overall requirements and exhibits a more balanced distribution between priority classes, suggesting either later-stage maturity or fewer immediate criticalities in the data orchestration layer.

Figure 13: Prioritisation Distribution of WP Requirements

This prioritization snapshot helps identify where the platform’s development focus currently lies and offers insights into what areas may require further alignment or reprioritization as implementation advances. It also serves as a reference for validation planning and dependency resolution in future deliverables. It is important to note that the current prioritization reflects an early-stage view, consistent with the evolving maturity of the platform components and use cases. Further alignment and refinement of priority levels are expected during the second iteration of the requirement elicitation process, as implementation progresses and validation inputs become available.

5. Conclusion and Next Steps

This deliverable marks the consolidated effort to establish the foundational requirements and early-stage design considerations for the RI-SCALE DEP. Building on the input from both technical and scientific stakeholders, it presents a comprehensive overview of the envisioned platform's mission, architectural framework, and initial implementation goals. The purpose has not been to define final specifications, but to ensure that subsequent development phases are aligned with the overarching objectives of the project, particularly those related to cross-infrastructure AI-driven data processing, accessibility, and operational sustainability.

The vision for the DEP is to serve as a modular, flexible, and reusable service layer for RIs lacking in-house compute capacity. It aims to bridge the gap between large-scale research data and the analytical environments required to exploit them, particularly by supporting AI-driven processing in a secure, FAIR-compliant, and federated setting. The platform's foundational purpose is to shift data reuse from a download-centric model to an embedded processing model, where compute and model capabilities are brought closer to the data. As detailed in [Section 2](#), this vision responds to key challenges faced by RIs, such as fragmented infrastructure, limited user access to computing resources, and the increasing complexity of analytical software stacks. Based on this vision, a set of high-level design principles was articulated ([Section 3](#)). These include a layered approach to deployment (ranging from single institution to federated DEP setups), a clear definition of user roles (end users, model developers, operators), and a functional separation of the platform's core responsibilities (data lifecycle management, AI execution, access control, and resource accounting). Furthermore, important non-functional principles were defined: alignment with community standards, user support strategies, and long-term maintainability through modular architecture.

The requirements consolidated in this deliverable (88 in total) form the foundation for aligning platform development with project goals. These requirements span both functional capabilities (e.g., model execution, access workflows) and non-functional attributes (e.g., security, performance, usability), and have been contributed across all key development WPs and scientific/technical use cases. This breadth of input highlights the strong engagement of both technical and user stakeholders in defining the platform. Notably, many of the functional requirements directly address the core design pillars identified earlier, especially in areas such as scalable AI support and integrated access control. At the same time, this set of requirements should be viewed as the first iteration of an evolving specification process. The platform and its use cases are still in an early maturity phase (M4), and as implementation efforts progress and validation scenarios become more concrete, further refinement will be necessary. Additional input from external stakeholders (WP6) and risk and compliance partners (WP1) is anticipated in the next phase.

Looking forward, the outcomes of this deliverable will directly guide the preparation of the Validation Plan for Use Cases (D5.2). Additionally, this deliverable is an input for deliverable D2.1 (DEP Data management specification and roadmap), D3.1 (AI systems and models specification and roadmap),

and D4.1 (Access management systems specification and roadmap), which respectively contribute to the implementation of D5.2. This next step will focus on translating high-level requirements into concrete validation scenarios and testable conditions, ensuring that each requirement is backed by clear acceptance criteria and traceability mechanisms. In parallel, the development teams will begin aligning their implementation activities with the consolidated requirements, laying the groundwork for the first DEP release (D5.3). Importantly, the second iteration of requirement elicitation will also revisit current priorities, filling any remaining gaps, particularly in usability, integration, and compliance, as the platform advances from conceptualisation to validation.

Annex I: Full List of Requirements

Functional Requirements

WP2 Functional Requirements

Requirement Jira key	Requirement Source	Description	Rationale	Component That Fulfils It	Priority
RSREQ-101	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	Infrastructure to operate the GROQ card in a testing/proof of concept environment	To test inference on GROQ TPU cards, they need to be run in an HPC environment	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)	Must
RSREQ-24	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	<p>The DEP should provide a centrally managed Git server based on GitLab, to support version control of training code, configuration files, and related project resources. This Git server should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be accessible from all computer sites of the DEP. • Be integrated with the DEP's user management system, ensuring that access control (e.g., project-based visibility, permissions, and roles) is centrally managed and aligned with the user's project membership and roles in the DEP. • Be suitable for both interactive use (via GitLab web interface) and scripted operations (via Git over SSH/HTTPS and CI/CD API integrations). • Support continuous integration (CI) pipelines for running automated jobs on the DEP compute infrastructure, including support for 	Collaborative AI model development within the DEP requires reliable, accessible, and secure version control for code and associated artifacts. A GitLab server provides users with a standard and widely adopted platform for collaborative development. The AI Model Hub needs a centralised repository to collect the code of tracked models. CI support, especially with GPU capabilities, further enhances automation and reproducibility of AI development. This requirement supports development in Use Cases 5 and 6, and contributes to KPI03: No. of AI frameworks/toolboxes offered within DEPs.	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)	Should

		GPU-enabled CI runners to allow automated testing to be executed as part of version-controlled workflows.			
RSREQ-25	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	<p>The DEP should provide a centrally managed container registry to support container-based workflows across all compute sites. The service should support Apptainer (formerly Singularity) containers. Examples of suitable solutions include Harbor or GitLab Container Registry. The registry should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be accessible from all DEP compute sites • Allow users to upload, version, and share container images associated with their projects, with access controlled via the DEP's user management system. • Ensure Apptainer containers can be executed on all supported compute infrastructures. 	Reliable container management is essential for reproducible, portable, and secure execution of AI workflows in the DEP. The AI Model Hub should use the container registry to execute tracked models. Furthermore, this directly supports collaborative development in use cases 5 and 6.	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)	Should
RSREQ-38	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	The DEP needs to be able to copy data onto at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cinceca), MN5 (Bsc)	<p>The technical use case states: Evaluate and measure the scale at which the DEP can work on a EuroHPC machine while serving a challenging AI model with large data from DestinE.</p> <p>Hence the DEP needs to be able to copy data onto at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cinceca), MN5 (Bsc)</p>	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)	Must
RSREQ-39	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	The DEP needs to be able to spawn virtual kubelets onto at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cinceca), MN5 (Bsc).	<p>The technical use case states: Evaluate and measure the scale at which the DEP can work on a EuroHPC machine while serving a</p>	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)	Must

			challenging AI model with large data from DestinE. Hence the DEP needs to be able to spawn virtual kubelets onto at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cineca), MN5 (Bsc)		
RSREQ-89	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Implement data transfer mechanisms and protocols at the computing sites.	Needed to get data from data owners to the computing infrastructure	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)	Must
RSREQ-90	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Implement federated authentication/authorisation protocol at the compute sites.	Need to give data owners secure access to computing sites	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)	Must
RSREQ-106	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The platform must allow to download climate datasets through customizable queries from different data platforms, such as those within the Copernicus Climate Data Store or through ESGF data platform.	This functionality is needed for extracting the data needed for training the ML model and for inference of downscaled data for use case WP3.3.	Data Discovery & Popularity Service (WP2-T2.3)	Must
RSREQ-18	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The platform should support access to usage statistics on ESM data (i.e., CMIP) through customizable queries, allowing also for basic aggregation functions.	This functionality is needed for (i) extracting the data needed for training the ML model and (ii) for feeding the trained model with the data for inference for the use case in WP3.3. It contributes KPI#4 (No. of AI models offered within DEPs), KPI#7 (No. of AI models trained in DEP pilots), KPI#8 (No. of use cases developed for DEP validation).	Data Discovery & Popularity Service (WP2-T2.3)	Should

RSREQ-45	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The Data Popularity service must provide a way for extracting the most downloaded ESM data (e.g., CMIP) from the ENES research infrastructure.	This functionality is needed for properly driving the data ingestion pipeline and supporting the DEP caching mechanism. It contributes to KPI#6 (Total size of datasets used in the DEP pilots).	Data Discovery & Popularity Service (WP2-T2.3)	Must
RSREQ-100	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The storage systems in RI-SCALE: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RI Data holdings (long-term storage). • Storage @ E-Infrastructure for dataset access. • Must support OIDC token authentication based on the work prepared in WP4. 	Without that support, the authentication of storage operations will be extremely difficult and fall outside the trust network built in WP4.	Data Holdings Integration Framework (WP2-T2.4)	Must
RSREQ-21	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The platform should support access to CMIP climate projections and reanalysis data.	This functionality is needed for extracting the data needed for training the ML model and for inference of downscaled data for use case WP3.3.	Data Holdings Integration Framework (WP2-T2.4)	Must
RSREQ-42	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	Newly generated DestinE training data should be retrieved to the DEP to make it available for AIFS training runs on at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cinceca), MN5 (Bsc)	There is also a performance component here, 100 Gb/s roughly between DEP and DestinE data holdings, data space. Hence, DEP should have enough storage available for the AIFS training datasets and transfer 50-100 TB in a few minutes (100 Gb/s) to at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cinceca), MN5 (Bsc)	Data Holdings Integration Framework (WP2-T2.4)	Must

<p>RSREQ-22</p>	<p>[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)</p>	<p>The DEP should provide a robust and secure process for orchestrating the transfer of Whole Slide Images (WSIs) from Research Infrastructure (RI) data holdings into the DEP. The entire orchestration should be declaratively defined and user-configurable, while abstracting away the complexity of backend transfer and storage operations.</p> <p>The orchestration process should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable RIs to define project-scoped staging rules, specifying which WSIs are to be transferred, using unique identifiers recognised across both the RI and the DEP. • Verify the successful and complete transfer of datasets before making them available to the user. • Support the transfer of associated metadata alongside WSIs, and provide functionality to resynchronise metadata independently, allowing RIs to update or extend metadata (e.g., annotations, genetic data) without requiring the WSIs to be re-transferred. • Track which WSIs have already been transferred to the DEP to avoid redundant transfers when multiple projects request the same images. • Support the definition of a data lifespan, allowing RIs or project owners to specify an expiry period after which the transferred data should be automatically deleted from the DEP. • Provide logging capabilities for all involved stakeholders, ideally accessible via a web 	<p>Transferring large-scale, sensitive WSI data from RI holdings into the DEP must be handled through a controlled and reliable process. Allowing RIs to define project-level dataset visibility ensures that governance and data access policies are enforced at the source. Automated transfer of WSIs will be used for the scientific use cases 5 and 6.</p>	<p>Data Orchestration Service (WP2-T2.1)</p>	<p>Should</p>
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		interface, to monitor the status of data transfers (e.g., when a transfer was initiated, completed, or failed).			
RSREQ-23	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	In addition to enabling the transfer of datasets from RIs into the DEP for analysis, the DEP should provide a Results Delivery Mechanism that allows research outputs - such as annotations, processed datasets, and derived results—to be automatically transferred back to the originating RI at a predefined point in time, such as the end of a project. All involved stakeholders should be able to monitor the status of these transfers, e.g., through a web interface. The specific research outputs to be returned should be jointly defined at the beginning of the project or in the usage agreement between the DEP user and the corresponding RI. The Results Delivery Mechanism should then automatically initiate the transfer of outputs at a scheduled date, e.g., project end.	Returning research outputs to the RI ensures that data products generated through DEP-based analysis are preserved, traceable, and available for future reuse. This closes the research data lifecycle and reinforces the role of RIs as long-term stewards of scientific data. It also aligns with the FAIR data principles—ensuring that outputs are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.	Data Orchestration Service (WP2-T2.1)	Should
RSREQ-91	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	EISCAT L1 and L2 (raw and spectral) data MUST be made accessible, following access rules as specified in the other SUC4 Requirements. EISCAT is using EGI Checkin and Perun to manage access authN/authZ. The existing download portal (portal.eiscat.se) is not very suitable for API download, so a WebDAV or similar service to be used with Rucio/FTS SHOULD be deployed. Any used tools MUST implement data access authZ through supported protocols. Existing portal retrieves VO group membership information by OIDC to EGI Checkin- this is the	Data accessibility	Data Orchestration Service (WP2-T2.1)	Must

		<p>preferred protocol.</p> <p>Analysed parameters (Level 3 data) are free for use, though and can preferably be filtered and retrieved using the Madrigal web services and Python client services.</p>			
RSREQ-92	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	<p>Model outputs must be returned to the S3 buckets of Hypermeteo, so that they can be used to provide climate services.</p>	<p>This functionality is required in order to exploit the data produced by Scientific Use Case 1 (downscaling of climate projections).</p>	Data Orchestration Service (WP2-T2.1)	Must
RSREQ-33	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	<p>During the data orchestration from RIs to the DEP, datasets must be prepared in a format that ensures they are ready for use in AI workflows and data analysis. This step acts as a bridge between raw data held at RIs and downstream exploitation in the DEP.</p> <p>For instance, this preparation should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform data conversion, if needed, e.g., convert WSIs to DICOM format. • Perform pseudo-anonymisation, if required by the RI, such as the removal of patient-identifying metadata. <p>Use case providers together with RIs should provide documentation specifying the acceptable data and metadata formats for their datasets, such that they are compatible with the DEP.</p>	<p>This requirement ensures that all data entering the DEP is consistently prepared and standardised, regardless of its origin or modality. Standardisation during data preparation is essential for enabling seamless integration with DEP tools, reproducibility of AI workflows, and interoperability across scientific use cases. It also reduces technical overhead for users and developers by ensuring that data is analysis-ready upon arrival.</p>	Data Preparation Module (WP2-T2.2)	Should

WP3 Functional Requirements

Requirement Jira key	Requirement Source	Description	Rationale	Component That Fulfils It	Priority
RSREQ-10	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The AI computing framework must support large-scale offloading of AI training and inference seamlessly across cloud and HPC infrastructure.	This ensures that the AI framework in the DEP is readily portable, which allows RIs to deploy it in their local machine, cloud provider, or a large HPC centre. It contributes directly to KPI#3, KPI#4 and KPI#7.	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)	Must
RSREQ-12	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The DEP must have a user-friendly interface that allows for seamless application and deployment for the use cases.	The value of a technology is determined by how effectively it is used in practice. Functionality and utility of the DEP, delivered by the Technical Team, must be sustained (project duration and beyond) and widespread (use-cases) application by the Scientific and Technical Use Cases and the associated end users.	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)	Should
RSREQ-17	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The platform must support the development, training, and deployment of ML models to learn patterns in data usage and transfer failures and predict changes/anomalies as required for the use case in T3.3.	This functionality is needed for implementing the use case in WP3.3 as well as validating the use case in WP5.2. It contributes KPI#7 (No. of AI models trained in DEP pilots) and KPI#8 (No. of use cases developed for DEP validation). Moreover, it is linked to KPI#4 (No. of AI models offered within DEPs).	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)	Must

<p>RSREQ-26</p>	<p>[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)</p>	<p>The DEP should integrate with the Itwinai workflow orchestration framework to support hyperparameter optimization (HPO) for AI models. Users should be able to define HPO tasks as part of their model training workflows and execute them on the DEP compute infrastructure. The HPO framework should allow users to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a search space for hyperparameters (e.g., learning rate, batch size, ...) • Choose from standard optimization strategies, such as grid search, random search, and Bayesian optimization. • Specify the objective metric to optimize (e.g., validation accuracy, AUC). • Set constraints on resource usage, including maximum number of trials, parallel runs, or GPU-hour budgets. • Enable early stopping of unpromising trials based on intermediate results to save computational resources. Supported strategies should include the Median stopping rule, Asynchronous Successive Halving (ASHA), and Hyperband. • Automatically deploy training jobs for each HPO trial to the DEP, without requiring manual submission by the user. 	<p>Hyperparameter optimization is essential for developing AI models. Supporting early stopping helps minimize waste of computing resources by stopping poorly performing trials early. This will be used for Use Case 5 and Use Case 6 and contributes to KPI03: No. of AI frameworks/toolboxes offered within DEPs.</p>	<p>AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)</p>	<p>Should</p>
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<p>RSREQ-27</p>	<p>[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)</p>	<p>The DEP should support the use of MLflow to track AI model training workflows executed within the platform. Users should be able to log metadata about each training run directly to an MLflow tracking server provided by the DEP. This tracking should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hyperparameters, such as learning rate, batch size, and number of epochs. • Performance metrics, such as accuracy, AUC, loss, or task-specific indicators. • Artifacts, such as trained model files, logs, and visualisations. • Environment metadata, including the Git commit hash of the training code and the container image identifier used for the run. • Dataset references, including internal DEP dataset IDs. <p>The tracking functionality should be accessible programmatically from within the training code (e.g., via the MLflow Python client) and operate seamlessly with training jobs launched on all DEP compute sites. Access to the web interface of MLflow should be controlled through the user management of the DEP. It should be asserted that users only have access to training logs and metadata of projects they are associated with.</p>	<p>MLflow provides an established mechanism for capturing and organising metadata during model training, which is essential for reproducibility, comparison of experiments, and responsible model development. For WSI-based AI workflows, where models may require significant tuning and iteration, the ability to track all aspects of training is critical. This requirement supports model development in Use Cases 5 and 6 and contributes to KPI03: No. of AI frameworks/toolboxes offered within DEPs.</p>	<p>AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)</p>	<p>Should</p>
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RSREQ-40	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	AIFS should be able to use at least some of the distributed ML frameworks on at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cinceca), MN5 (Bsc)	The technical use case states: Evaluate and measure the scale at which the DEP can work on a EuroHPC machine while serving a challenging AI model with large data from DestinE. Hence, AIFS should be able to use at least some of the distributed ML frameworks on at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cinceca), MN5 (BSC)	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)	Must
RSREQ-96	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The platform must support the development, training, and deployment of ML models to learn spatial patterns in climate projections and predict high-resolution climate scenarios as required for the use case in T3.3.	This functionality is needed for implementing the use case in WP3.3 as well as validating the use case in WP5.2. It contributes KPI#7 (No. of AI models trained in DEP pilots) and KPI#8 (No. of use cases developed for DEP validation). Moreover, it is linked to KPI#4 (No. of AI models offered within DEPs).	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)	Must
RSREQ-20	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The platform must support the development, training, and deployment of ML models (probably CNNs) to perform statistical downscaling of climate projections at higher spatial resolution.	This functionality is needed for the implementation of one of the scientific use cases in WP3.3 and for the validation of the use case in WP5.2. It contributes KPI#7 (No. of AI models trained in DEP pilots) and KPI#8 (No. of use cases developed for DEP validation). Moreover, it is linked to KPI#4 (No. of AI models offered within DEPs).	AI for Environmental Science (WP3-T3.3)	Must

RSREQ-95	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The project must provide a ML-based model for enabling prediction and/or detection of changes/anomalies in the usage of climate data from ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation). ML models can be effectively used to learn from historical data usage and transfer log patterns associated with usage and anomalies. The trained model will then be applied to current data usage streams, for example, to identify the most used data in a given period or react based on anomaly detection of high loads in the data downloads.	This functionality is needed for implementing the use case in WP3.3 as well as validating the use case in WP5.2. It contributes KPI#7 (No. of AI models trained in DEP pilots) and KPI#8 (No. of use cases developed for DEP validation). Moreover, it is linked to KPI#4 (No. of AI models offered within DEPs).	AI for Environmental Science (WP3-T3.3)	Must
RSREQ-15	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The platform must support foundational model training and inference execution on data from the BioImage Archive	This functionality is essential for Scientific use case 7 (Foundational models for heterogeneous biological image data). Also, to train foundation models for heterogeneous image data, as required on T3.4; It directly contributes to KPI#7 (No. of AI models trained in DEP pilots) and KPI#8 (No. of use cases developed for DEP validation).	AI for Health and Life Sciences (WP3-T3.4)	Must
RSREQ-16	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The platform must enable fine-tuning models on data from the BioImage Archive	This functionality is essential for Scientific use case 7 (Foundational models for heterogeneous biological image data). Also to fine-tune models for image classification, segmentation and anomaly detection, as required on T3.4; It directly contributes to KPI#8 (No. of use cases developed for DEP validation).	AI for Health and Life Sciences (WP3-T3.4)	Must

RSREQ-31	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	<p>In the DEP, algorithms should be developed for survival prediction based on Whole Slide Image (WSI) data. These algorithms should estimate patient outcomes using visual patterns in histopathological slides. The models should be implemented using reproducible workflows and make use of the training and orchestration tools provided by the DEP compute infrastructure. The developed models should produce predictions that are interpretable, allowing validation and assessment by pathologists.</p> <p>To ensure scientific relevance and robustness, validation should be performed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On publicly available survival prediction benchmarks to demonstrate the novelty and competitiveness of the developed algorithms against the current state of the art. • On the colorectal cancer cohort available within the DEP, which includes WSIs of lymph node tissue, provided by MUG and MMCI, with the aim of supporting the potential identification of novel biomarkers. 	<p>Developing survival prediction algorithms within the DEP highlights how RI data can be leveraged to address clinically relevant research challenges. The colorectal cancer use case demonstrates this approach in practice and contributes directly to RI-SCALE Use Case 5 and KPI#4 (No. of AI models offered within DEPs). Furthermore, the potential identification of novel biomarkers through model interpretation and validation may result in new scientific insights, contributing to KPI21: No. of peer-reviewed scientific publications and KPI22: No. of research outputs.</p>	AI for Health and Life Sciences (WP3-T3.4)	Should
RSREQ-32	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	<p>Algorithms should be developed for generating synthetic histopathological images using generative AI models, such as diffusion-based approaches. These models should be trained on real pathology data available within the DEP. To ensure scientific relevance and output quality, validation of the generated synthetic images should include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy risk assessment, e.g., membership inference testing, to confirm that synthetic 	<p>This requirement contributes to use case 6 and supports KPI#4 (No. of AI models offered within DEPs), KPI#21 (No. of peer-reviewed scientific publications), and KPI#22 (No. of research outputs).</p>	AI for Health and Life Sciences (WP3-T3.4)	Should

		<p>images do not expose identifiable patient information.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A user study with pathologists, who will review synthetic images and assess their realism, diagnostic plausibility, and fitness for research or training. 			
RSREQ-87	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	<p>The DEP must enable to send any analysis outputs and model metadata back to the BIA. Model outputs and metadata must be returned to the BIA using a consistent schema so they can be used to support automated data categorisation and similarity search within the RI</p>	<p>This functionality is essential for Scientific use case 7 (Foundational models for heterogeneous biological image data). It directly contributes to KPI#8 (No. of use cases developed for DEP validation).</p>	AI for Health and Life Sciences (WP3-T3.4)	Must
RSREQ-13	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	<p>The AI Model Hub component must provide REST APIs and a basic Web UI for core model lifecycle operations (upload, discovery, versioning, retrieval) using Hypha and MLflow as a backend. It must enable the storage and API-based retrieval of key provenance metadata (e.g., creator, date, dataset reference, parameters/environment, license) with each model version, and offer interfaces to initiate model benchmarking.</p>	<p>Fulfils the task requirements for delivering an AI Model Hub capable of storing, serving, and benchmarking models, incorporating a provenance model, and leveraging Hypha and MLflow. This supports model sharing, reproducibility, transparency, and trustworthiness, contributing to project goals and potential KPIs related to model management and usage.</p>	AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2)	Must
RSREQ-14	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	<p>The AI Model Hub must integrate with the central RI-SCALE Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI), anticipated to be the Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1), to enforce access control. Authorization decisions for all Hub functionalities and resources must be governed by policies managed within this AAI.</p>	<p>Directly addresses the task requirement to establish Authentication/Authorisation mechanisms for enforcing model access policies. This ensures secure and governed access to AI models within the Hub, aligning with project security requirements and potential</p>	AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2)	Must

			KPIs for controlled resource access and compliance.		
RSREQ-28	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The AI Model Hub should let users launch inference on any supported data modality via web UI or API. Inputs include dataset IDs, a chosen model, and run-time parameters (e.g., resolution, tile size). Workloads are sharded into parallel jobs (e.g., via itwinai) to scale on large datasets. The service must honour DEP’s user-management and ACL rules, ensuring users access only authorised data and models. Results are cached and reused whenever the same model, parameters and data recur, regardless of project or requester. Foundation models are integrated, and external ones requiring Hugging Face keys use the caller’s key at run time.	Simple and scalable WSI inference through the AI Model Hub is a key component of the DEP and essential for a good user experience. Foundation models will be used in Use Case 5, and the requirement contributes to KPI04: Number of AI models offered within DEPs.	AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2)	Must
RSREQ-94	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The assistant should enable users to perform basic bioimage analysis tasks, such as segmentation or object detection, through a conversational interface. Users should be able to upload images or select existing datasets, request a supported analysis (e.g., “Segment cells using CellPose”), and receive both visual and downloadable results.	Many users accessing RI imaging data do not have the technical expertise to deploy AI models or run analysis workflows independently. This requirement aims to provide a simplified interface for triggering standard analysis tasks, improving usability and promoting broader adoption of AI tools in image-based research.	AI Model Hub (WP3-T3.2)	Should

WP4 Functional Requirements

Requirement Jira key	Requirement Source	Description	Rationale	Component That Fulfils It	Priority
RSREQ-105	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distribute credits to users based on their calculated resource consumption and environmental impact. • Apply predefined rules to assign credits, prioritizing sustainable practices and efficient usage. • Provide a structured process for requesting additional credits (Credit Request > Approval Workflow > Post approval actions) • Support both manual assignment by authorized managers and automated distribution based on rules or quotas. • Allocation metadata recording(such as validity period and source pool). 	Distributing credits based on resource consumption and environmental impact, with predefined rules and structured request processes, promotes sustainable practices, ensures fair and transparent allocation, and supports flexible management through manual and automated methods while tracking metadata for accountability.	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Must
RSREQ-44	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect usage metrics for GPU, CPU, storage, network transfer, and AI model resources. • Record usage units for each resource type at a specified granularity level in the time domain. • Support tracking for cross-national and international DEP projects. • Usage captured on a per-user and per-project basis. 	Accurately collecting and recording usage metrics for GPU, CPU, storage, network transfer, and AI model resources is essential for effective resource management, operational transparency, and cost accountability, especially in large-scale, multi-tenant environments. Capturing these metrics at a specified time granularity ensures the ability to analyse usage trends, detect anomalies, and optimize resource allocation. Tracking usage on a per-user and per-project basis supports detailed billing, quota	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Must

			enforcement, and audit trails, which are critical for compliance, especially in regulated or international contexts.		
RSREQ-75	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capture ‘environmental impact units’ for each resource type (e.g., energy consumption, carbon footprint). • Integrate with external environmental impact data sources or models to enrich metrics. • Provide standardized environmental impact metrics across all DEP providers. 	Measuring environmental impact is critical to encourage sustainable usage and align with global sustainability goals (e.g., EU Green Deal). Standardized metrics ensure consistency across providers, addressing the challenge of varying environmental data formats.	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Must
RSREQ-76	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convert usage and environmental impact units into a unified credit system. • Define rules for credit allocation based on resource consumption and environmental impact and policy-based at the organizational level. • Support configurable credit models to encourage environmentally friendly usage and target each individual DEP. 	Converting usage and environmental impact into a unified credit system, with rules defined at the organizational level and configurable models, promotes sustainable practices and supports diverse DEP business needs, such as virtual access funds, by aligning incentives with green computing goals.	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Must
RSREQ-77	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable validation of usage and environmental impact metrics through scientific use cases. • Support iterative feedback loops to refine credit models based on validation results. 	Validation ensures the accuracy and reliability of usage and environmental metrics, and credits, addressing the challenge of ensuring trust in the system. Iterative feedback supports continuous improvement, aligning with user and provider needs.	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Must
RSREQ-78	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	Documented feedback shall be provided to refine access policies and virtual access fund allocations.	Feeding experiences into future provisioning plans ensures the DEP ecosystem evolves based on real-world usage and performance data, addressing the challenge of aligning	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Should

			infrastructure and policies with actual user needs and environmental goals.		
RSREQ-47	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Enable processing of decentralized identities using protocols such as SIOPv2, OID4VCI, and OID4VP.	Supporting decentralized identity protocols like SIOPv2, OID4VCI, and OID4VP enhances user privacy by enabling self-managed identities, ensures interoperability with global standards, and strengthens security through cryptographic verification, reducing fraud and fostering trust across ecosystems.	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-48	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Extend IAM systems (e.g., Check-in/Keycloak) to support WP5 distributed identity use cases.	Supports pilot use cases in WP5 (use case needs).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-49	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Implement a decentralized trust infrastructure including trust anchors, accreditation, and trust marks.	Ensures a trusted environment across systems (technical limitation).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-50	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Ensure GAIA-X compliance for trust relationships and credential issuer verification.	Addresses compliance requirements with GAIA-X (KPI, technical limitation).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-53	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Enable technical interoperability with initiatives such as EHDS, EOSC, and GAIA-X.	Ensures alignment with the external ecosystem (use case needs, KPI).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-54	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Test and validate interoperability for secure data transfers using Rucio and FTS.	Validates secure data exchange mechanisms (technical limitation).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Should

RSREQ-55	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Define and enforce access and usage policies using the ODRL standard.	Provides flexible data governance (use case needs).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Should
RSREQ-57	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Support integration with federated data spaces to test interoperability with external entities.	Enables advanced data sharing scenarios (use case needs).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Could
RSREQ-36	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	Download/access of raw/spectral EISCAT data (Levels 1/2) must follow EISCAT embargo rules, i.e., accessed data can only be processed and data can be shared/distributed only according to embargo rules set by the EISCAT agreements. This applies mainly to measurements newer than 3 years; older archived data will be free for use in the project. (See present EISCAT Portal, which implements Checkin/Perun OIDC client / using OIDC Claims)	Compliance with the EISCAT Data Policy.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must
RSREQ-71	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Support data access policies based on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identity assurance (e.g., verified user identity) • User attributes (e.g., groups & roles, organisation affiliation, nationality) • Data attributes (e.g., sensitivity level, ethics committee approval, data access policy) • Credit capacity (e.g., user quotas/limits) 	The requirement for extended data access policies is critical to delivering a secure, compliant, and flexible authorisation system. By enabling policies based on identity assurance, user and data attributes, and credit capacity, the system ensures fine-grained access control, regulatory compliance, and efficient resource management.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must

RSREQ-72	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Provide a standardised, expressive policy language that supports the creation of complex access control rules.	The requirement for a standardised, expressive policy language is essential to support the creation of complex access control rules, enabling fine-grained authorisation based on diverse criteria, such as user attributes (e.g. nationality, organisation), data attributes (e.g. sensitivity level, acceptance of ethics committee approval, data access policy), and credit capacity. A standardised language ensures consistency, interoperability, and maintainability, allowing for development, testing, and updating policies efficiently.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must
RSREQ-73	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Provide a policy engine that supports: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic evaluation of access policies in real-time (or near real-time) • Hierarchical management of policies (e.g., parent-child policy structures or precedence rules) 	A policy engine with dynamic evaluation and hierarchical management is essential for efficient authorisation. Dynamic evaluation ensures real-time access decisions, while hierarchical management simplifies policy organisation and maintenance.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must
RSREQ-74	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Enable logging of policy decisions for traceability. Provide auditing capabilities to track access control decisions and policy evaluations. Log collection and querying should be done using an industry-standard solution.	Logging and auditing of policy decisions are essential for ensuring traceability and accountability in the authorisation system. Logging enables recording access control decisions, supporting troubleshooting, security incident analysis, and compliance with regulatory requirements (e.g., GDPR). Auditing capabilities allow tracking of	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must

			policy evaluations, ensuring transparency and verifiability of access decisions.		
RSREQ-82	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Provide a user interface that allows administrators to author, edit, and manage access control policies easily. Such interface would ideally be dynamic enough to support the introduction of new policies without the need for excessive new development.	An intuitive user interface is valuable for enabling administrators to manage complex access control policies with ease, abstracting the policy language’s complexity.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Could
RSREQ-97	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The AI compute framework, provided by T3.1, should be allowed to be deployed with relative ease on at least some of the EuroHPC systems. This has to do with both T3.1 and AAI from WP4.	TBA	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Should
RSREQ-65	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	A user interface should be available to get the information from the users, like organisation names and countries.	Collection of data from the users.	Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3)	Must
RSREQ-67	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	A user interface should show the information intended for the users.	Obligation to inform the users.	Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3)	Must
RSREQ-68	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	A user interface should collect consent from the users.	Obligation to get the users' consent.	Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3)	Must

Non-Functional Requirements

WP2 Non-Functional Requirements

Requirement Jira key	Requirement Source	Description	Rationale	Component That Fulfils It	Priority
RSREQ-41	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	Provide enough storage space and throughput to serve data for AIFS training in a timely manner	The technical use case states: Evaluate and measure the scale at which the DEP can work on a EuroHPC machine while serving a challenging AI model with large data from DestinE. Hence, DEP should have enough storage available for the AIFS training datasets and transfer 50-100 TB in a few minutes (100 Gb/s) to at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cineca), MN5 (BSC)	Computing Site Integration Interface (WP2-T2.5)	Must
RSREQ-46	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The Data Popularity service should provide an easy-to-use interface (e.g., UI Dashboard or API-based) to support the extraction of information about the most downloaded data in an easy and quick manner.	The ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation) Data Statistics service continuously collects information about data usage from the ESGF data nodes. Therefore, providing an easy way for querying and retrieving information from the service is key to efficiently and effectively supporting the DEP data lifecycle management.	Data Discovery & Popularity Service (WP2-T2.3)	Should

WP3 Non-Functional Requirements

Requirement Jira key	Requirement Source	Description	Rationale	Component That Fulfils It	Priority
RSREQ-102	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	The GROQ cards being tested need to be accessible and usable via appropriate interfaces and/or software elements	To use GROQ cards in inference, we assume the software layers need to be adapted	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)	Should
RSREQ-11	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The AI computing framework should be able to integrate all RIs and scale efficiently (>80%) to more than 100 GPUs.	This benchmark demonstrates the versatility of the AI framework and its large-scale training capabilities. It contributes directly to KPI#4 and also to KPI#6, to enable training with large-scale datasets.	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)	Should
RSREQ-29	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	Users of the DEP should be able to automatically deploy an instance of the WSI visualization toolkit, XOpac. The viewer is deployed in an Apptainer container. In this container, directories for the following data should be mounted: WSIS that the user has access to, the algorithm output of the user, and a directory where the viewer saves annotations. The algorithm output should be writable by compute jobs while the viewer is running, enabling real-time monitoring of results during training. The viewer's web interface is exposed through a URL, where access is controlled through the user management of the DEP. XOpac enables users to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zoom, pan, and navigate in gigapixel-sized WSIs with minimal latency by streaming only the visible viewport instead of full images. 	User experience is improved through seamless interaction of WSIs and algorithm results directly in the DEP platform. Having an in-platform viewer is essential, as it is impractical to download terabyte-scale datasets to local machines for visualisation. Moreover, it ensures sensitive data remains within the secure DEP environment while still allowing users to interact with it effectively. XOpac will be used in the scientific validation (Task 5.2) of Use Cases 5 and 6, and contributes to KPI03: No. of AI frameworks/toolboxes offered within DEPs.	AI Computing Framework (WP3-T3.1)	Should

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create pixel-level annotations on WSIs, which can be used as training data for algorithms. • Visualize algorithm outputs on WSIs, such as heatmaps or segmentations. 			
RSREQ-19	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	The ML model should be efficient enough to be potentially applied for real-time detection of anomalies in data usage streams, when deployed in the infrastructure.	Real-time prediction can support early detection of changes in data usage patterns. This could allow RI managers to deal with high loads in data download patterns and react to potential issues connected with data transfer failures in a timely manner.	AI for Environmental Science (WP3-T3.3)	Could
RSREQ-86	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	Advanced image compression for histopathology, Whole Slide Images should be investigated. The goal is to enhance DEP storage and transfer efficiency without harming diagnostic value or model accuracy. In particular, JPEG2000 should be evaluated, focusing on the effects of AI training, inference, and processing speed.	Histopathological images, particularly WSIs, require large storage and are expensive to transfer across infrastructures. Efficient compression reduces system load and speeds up data access, while preserving image quality is essential for clinical validation and trustworthy AI development. This technical use case contributes to optimising the DEP's performance and supports sustainability, interoperability, and usability across health science domains.	AI for Health and Life Sciences (WP3-T3.4)	Should

WP4 Non-Functional Requirements

Requirement Jira key	Requirement Source	Description	Rationale	Component That Fulfils It	Priority
RSREQ-79	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Handle high volumes of usage data from multiple DEP providers and users. Support scaling to accommodate the growing number of cross-national projects. 	Scalability is necessary to manage increasing data loads as DEP adoption grows, addressing the technical challenge of processing large-scale, distributed usage metrics without performance degradation.	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Should
RSREQ-80	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Process and record usage and environmental metrics with low latency. Fast credit report generation for typical queries. 	Low latency ensures a responsive system, improving user experience for providers and end users. Rapid report generation enhances functionality and maintains smooth interoperability with other connected modules.	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Should
RSREQ-81	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement data redundancy to prevent loss of usage or credit data. 	Redundancy protects against data loss, ensuring operational continuity.	Credit Management System (WP4-T4.4)	Should
RSREQ-34	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	Data to be used as input for scheduling decisions. Requires selecting the data needed, identifying their sources, investigating access methods and access policies.	We cannot make decisions without data to base these decisions on.	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-58	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Ensure secure identity handling and data transfer using mechanisms like end-to-end encryption and zero-knowledge proofs.	Protects sensitive data and ensures confidentiality (KPI, compliance needs).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-59	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The system must scale to handle a growing number of identities, credentials, and interoperability use cases.	Ensures system performance under load (technical limitation).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must

RSREQ-60	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Use standard interfaces and protocols such as OpenID, OAuth 2.0, and W3C DIDs to ensure compatibility.	Promotes long-term maintainability and integration (technical limitation).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-62	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Ensure a modular system architecture that allows easy updates and integration of new protocols.	Reduces maintenance effort and supports future requirements (technical limitation).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Should
RSREQ-63	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	All identity and credential transactions must be auditable and logged for traceability.	Ensures accountability and compliance (KPI, compliance needs).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-64	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Ensure compliance with GDPR regarding data minimization, purpose limitation, and user consent.	Addresses legal and regulatory obligations (compliance needs).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Must
RSREQ-66	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Fulfil the technical and policy requirements defined by EHDS, GAIA-X, and EOSC.	Supports project visibility and external cooperation (KPI, use case needs).	Interoperability Module for Data Spaces (WP4-T4.2)	Should
RSREQ-103	[ISU] Internal – Scientific Use Case (Scientific UC)	For data on the DEP access policies from the RIs should be enforced. For instance, it should be ensured that each transfer is associated with the relevant project context and that only authorised users and processes can initiate or access the transferred data.	Ensuring that data on the DEP can only be accessed by users with the respective rights is necessary to account for policies defined by the RIs.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Should
RSREQ-43	[ITU] Internal – Technical Use Case (Technical UC)	The data access model for DestinE should be respected, this probably means federation with the DestinE AIM system (customized Keycloak)	DestinE has a strict data access policy that needs to be respected by any component that holds that data and makes it available to third parties. We can envision also a setup where the data is	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must

			maybe not kept in the DEP, but only the orchestration is handled by the DEP, still, access control should be in place and compliant with DestinE access policies. Hence, DEP should have enough storage available for the AIFS training datasets and transfer 50-100 TB in a few minutes (100 Gb/s) to at least one of the EuroHPC systems that DestinE is currently using, Lumi (CSC), Leonardo (Cineca), MN5 (Bsc)		
RSREQ-83	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The authorisation solution must scale to handle large numbers of users, policies, and access requests efficiently	Scalability is essential to ensure the authorisation solution manages growing users, policies, and requests efficiently. It allows for maintaining performance under high loads.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must
RSREQ-84	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The policy engine should evaluate policies dynamically with low latency to support real-time access control decisions	Low-latency policy evaluation is essential to ensure the policy engine delivers real-time (or near real-time) access control decisions.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must
RSREQ-85	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The authorisation solution should integrate seamlessly with existing systems and frameworks for identity management, data storage, and access control. It must support interoperability with common protocols such as OpenID Connect, OAuth2, and SAML, as well as frameworks like ODRL and Verifiable Credentials (VCs) to enable fine-grained, standards-based policy enforcement across distributed environments.	Interoperability enables the authorisation solution to integrate with existing identity, storage, and access systems, leveraging current infrastructure and ensuring consistent, scalable policy enforcement.	Policy-Based Authorization Framework (WP4-T4.1)	Must
RSREQ-104	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The personal data should be encrypted at rest.	Cybersecurity: data transmission	Privacy-First Compliance	Should

				Layer (WP4-T4.3)	
RSREQ-52	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	A secure token is transmitted for each request to the IAM system.	Authentication and authorization.	Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3)	Must
RSREQ-56	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The personal data should be encrypted in transit.	Cybersecurity: data transmission	Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3)	Must
RSREQ-69	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	Each token should be revoked in a proper way.	Authentication and authorization.	Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3)	Must
RSREQ-70	[ITT] Internal – Technical Team	The actions related to consent and to token revocation should be incorporated in the logs.	Authentication and authorization.	Privacy-First Compliance Layer (WP4-T4.3)	Must